

AXIAL LENGTH CHANGES AFTER SHORT TERM EXPOSURE TO BLUE LIGHT AMONG EMMETROPES WITH OPTICALLY INDUCE HYPEROPIC DEFOCUS

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Abstract

Objective: The study aimed to measure the transient axial length (AXL) changes after short-term exposure to blue light before and after hyperopic defocus. **Methodology:** An interventional study design (quasi-experimental pre and post-interventional design) was conducted at Al-Shifa Trust Eye Hospital among optometry students using a non-probability judgmental sampling technique. Visual acuity was measured with LogMAR, and refractive status was determined with a Retinoscope. Blue light exposure was administered using a Blue Laser Pointer emitting a 405nm wavelength. Hyperopic defocus was induced using a -3.00DS lens in a trial frame. The IOL Master Zeiss 700 was used to measure the AXL. Data were entered and analyzed through online web-based software, Data tab. **Results:** A total of 30 subjects, including 06 (20%) males and 24 (80%) females, with a mean age of 20.67 ± 0.96 , participated in the study. Comparing Pre-defocus Axial length (PDAXL) and After Defocus Axial length (ADAXL) following 30 seconds (23.2 ± 0.69 , 23.19 ± 0.68 , $p 0.006$), 60 seconds (23.2 ± 0.68 , 23.2 ± 0.68 , $p 0.056$), and 90 seconds (23.2 ± 0.69 , 23.2 ± 0.69 , $p 0.002$) of exposure to blue light, a statistically significant difference was observed among the 30-second and 90-second exposure groups ($p 0.006$ and $p 0.002$, respectively), but not among the 60-second group ($p 0.056$). **Conclusion:** The study concludes that short-wavelength exposure and hyperopic defocus together cause axial length shortening, which could be employed to manage myopia progression.

Keywords: Axial Length, Blue Light, Myopia, Optical Defocus.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the widespread use of digital devices and increased exposure to artificial light sources have raised concerns about their potential impact on visual health.^{[1],[2]} One area of investigation has been the effect of blue light, emitted by electronic devices, on axial length changes among individuals with optically induced hyperopic defocus.

Axial length, the distance from the anterior cornea to the posterior sclera, plays a critical role in determining the refractive status of the eye.^[3] Changes in axial length have been associated with refractive errors such as myopia and hyperopia. However, the effects of blue light on axial length, particularly in individuals with hyperopic defocus, have remained relatively unexplored.^[4]

Previous studies have reported conflicting findings regarding the effects of blue light on ocular health.^[1] Some studies suggested that blue light exposure contributed to increased myopia progression, while others proposed a potential protective effect. However, few studies specifically focused on the influence of blue light on axial length changes in individuals with hyperopic defocus. Thus, this research aimed to bridge this gap in knowledge and provide a more comprehensive understanding of the relationship between blue light exposure and axial length alterations in this specific population.

This study aimed to examine the short-term effects of blue light exposure on axial length changes among emmetropes with optically induced hyperopic defocus. Emmetropes, individuals with normal refractive status, served as an essential control group for assessing the influence of blue light on axial length independent of pre-existing refractive errors. Understanding the potential effects of blue light on axial length changes is crucial for developing appropriate preventive strategies and interventions to mitigate the risks associated with prolonged exposure to blue light. Furthermore, this research could have implications for refractive error management and inform clinical decisions regarding blue light filtering technologies.

METHODOLOGY

This interventional study employed a quasi-experimental pre and post-interventional design at Al-Shifa Trust Eye Hospital, focusing on students of Optometry selected through a non-probability judgmental sampling technique. The subjects, aged between 19 and 23 years, were considered emmetropes if they had a Spherical Equivalent Refraction (SER) ranging from at least less than +0.50DS to -0.50DS, and a Log MAR VA of 0.0.^[5] Axial length was defined as the distance measured with the IOL Master between the anterior cornea and the retinal pigment epithelium (RPE).^[6] Hyperopic defocus was induced by placing a concave lens of -3.00 Diopter sphere in front of the eye.^[7] Visual acuity was measured using a standard Log MAR chart, and refractive status was determined with a Retinoscope (Heine 200). Exposure to blue light was provided by a Blue Laser Pointer emitting a 405nm wavelength. Axial length was measured using the IOL Master Zeiss 700. Data were entered and analyzed using the online web software "Data tab." The study

was conducted following the principles of the Helsinki Declaration, and informed consent was obtained from all study subjects, ensuring data confidentiality.

Subjects with normal eye health and emmetropia were recruited from the diagnostic division of ASETH at the Pakistan Institute of Ophthalmology. To minimize the effect of diurnal variability on axial length, all measurements were taken between 8:30 a.m. and 12:30 p.m., according to Pakistani standard time. Additionally, participants were required to abstain from alcohol, caffeine, and nicotine for 12 hours before the experiment. To eliminate any lingering effects from previous visual tasks, each individual spent 10 minutes in a dark room before the experiment. The baseline measurement of axial length was taken from the right eye using the IOL-MASTER 700 after the 10-minute washout period. After the axial length measurements, the right eye was exposed to blue light with a shorter wavelength for 30, 60, and 90 seconds. The IOL MASTER 700 was used to assess axial lengths at baseline, 30s, 60s, and 90s after stimulus offset from the right eye, while the level of induced defocus was kept constant throughout the trial by leaving the right eye undilated.

Descriptive Analysis: Mean and Standard Deviation (SD) were calculated for axial length measurements before and after defocus. For inferential Analysis: Data were analyzed for group comparison using the dependent paired sample t-test. The significance level was set at 0.05.

RESULTS

A total of 30 eyes from 30 subjects participated in this study, including 6 males (20%) and 24 females (80%). Only the right eye of each patient was considered. The mean age of the participants was 20 years (SD=10.02). The age range was between 19 and 23 years. All 30 participants included in the study were emmetropic and had normal ocular health.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics among Both Genders

		Gender	
		F	M
	Frequency	24	6
	%	80%	20%
Age	Mean	20.54	21.17
	Std. Deviation	0.98	0.75
	Minimum	19	20
	Maximum	23	22

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of Pre-defocus Axial Length (PDAXL) & After Defocus Axial Length (ADAXL) Focus after Blue Light Exposure for 30, 60 & 9 Sec

	N	Mean Std. Deviation	T	Df	p (2-tailed)
PDAXL 30sec. ADAXL 30sec.	30	23.2±0.69 23.2±0.68	2.98	29	.006
PDAXL 60sec. ADAXL 60sec.	30	23.2±0.68 23.2±0.68	1.99	29	.056
PDAXL 90sec. ADAXL 90sec.	30	23.2±0.69 23.2±0.69	3.32	29	.002

DISCUSSION

This study aimed to investigate the combined effects of shorter wavelength exposure and hyperopic defocus on the axial length of the eye. Previous research has shown that exposure to blue light leads to axial shortening, while hyperopic defocus results in axial elongation.

The present study observed changes in ocular biometry in response to blue light, particularly in the presence of lens-induced hyperopic defocus. The results revealed that exposure to blue light reduced the axial length of the defocused eye and mitigated the impact of hyperopic defocus. In blue light conditions, defocused eyes exhibited a decrease in axial length, accompanied by an increase in choroid thickness. These findings align with similar studies conducted on guinea pigs and chicks, providing further support for the conclusions drawn in this research.

Studies by Jiang et al. and Yu et al. demonstrated that lens-induced hyperopic defocus under blue light prevented axial elongation in animal models. Similar observations were made in chicks, where the application of a negative lens under red light resulted in a reduction in choroidal thickness, but no such effect was observed under blue light.^{[8],[9],[10]}

Previous research suggests that the rate of change in axial length varies depending on the type of defocus, with the eye elongating more rapidly during hyperopic defocus compared to the shortening observed during myopic defocus. Moreover, the effects of myopic defocus on axial length appear to be slightly more persistent during the subsequent period of clear vision following defocus.

Young adults' eyes showed the ability to rapidly detect defocus, adjusting their axial length within minutes of exposure to compensate. These findings are consistent with earlier studies conducted on both humans and animals,^{[11][12]} which observed alterations in axial length and choroidal thickness shortly after exposure to blur.^{[8],[11]} Previous research suggests that the rate of change in axial length varies depending on the type of defocus, with the eye elongating more rapidly during hyperopic defocus compared to the shortening observed during myopic defocus. Moreover, the effects of myopic defocus on axial length appear to be slightly more persistent during the subsequent period of clear vision following defocus.^[9]

In the present investigation, it was observed that following a recovery period of 20 minutes, the changes in axial length induced by light exposure offset and/or removal of defocus returned to baseline values. While the change in axial length observed under blue light conditions was within the repeatability range of the biometry used in this study (0.01 mm), the majority of subjects experienced axial length reduction in response to blue light exposure.^[13] These results contribute to our understanding of how the spectrum of light influences ocular growth in humans. Notably, the significant shortening of axial length under blue light, even in the presence of hyperopic defocus, supports the proposition that chromatic signals associated with LCA (Longitudinal Chromatic Aberration) may not be necessary to regulate temporary or short-term eye growth.^[10]

If the visual system employs chromatic cues to regulate ocular growth, the presence of a negative lens, which shifts the focal plane of all three wavelengths (red, green, and blue), should have resulted in an asymmetrical increase in axial length under different light exposures. Specifically, red light exposure would be expected to cause the greatest increase in axial length, followed by green light exposure, while blue light exposure would lead to the least increase. However, even in the presence of hyperopic defocus under blue light conditions, which typically induces axial elongation in humans, the negative lens failed to increase axial length. Instead, a brief period of exposure to blue light resulted in a significant decrease in axial length and thickening of the choroid. The underlying mechanism by which blue light inhibits ocular growth in humans remains unknown, although several non-LCA mechanisms have been proposed, including the blue cone-mediated ON-pathway,^[14] reduced retinoic acid levels,^[15] intrinsic photosensitivity of retinal ganglion cells (ipRGCs), in-focus/out-of-focus images, and increased depth of focus due to pupil constriction. Nevertheless, the exact process in humans has yet to be fully elucidated. Considering the positive linear relationship between pupil diameter and the size of the blur circle on the retina,^[16] it is possible that the size of the blur circle under various lighting conditions affects ocular size.

The spectral composition of ambient light is one of several factors that differ between indoor and outdoor environments.^[17] The presence of blue-enriched natural light outdoors and reduced amounts of red light have been hypothesized as potential factors contributing to the lower risk of myopia associated with spending time outdoors.^[18] It is speculated that altering the light spectrum under artificial conditions may also influence ocular growth and refractive changes, particularly due to the observed effects of blue light in our study.

Czepita and colleagues reported a higher prevalence of hyperopia in children whose homes were lit with fluorescent lighting (which has emission spectra closer to blue light) compared to tungsten-like lighting (which has emission spectra closer to red light). It has also been suggested that using blue lenses that absorb longer wavelengths when working up close or reading on paper could be protective against myopia.^[5]^[19] Similarly, myopia management spectacles with lower wavelength light transmission are currently being developed.^[20] Further investigation is needed to explore the potential of blue light

exposure strategies and adjusting indoor artificial light to be closer to blue light for myopia prevention.

The findings of the present study should be considered in light of a few limitations. Firstly, the study focused on a single type of defocus (-3.00 D). Future research replicating these experiments with diffusers to simulate form deprivation and positive lenses to induce myopic defocus may provide deeper insights into how the spectral composition of ambient light affects individuals. Additionally, human eyes work binocularly, with complementary effects between the two eyes, unlike the independently functioning eyes of animals such as fish, chicks, mice, and tree shrews. In our study, we induced monocular hyperopic anisometric blur and observed similar patterns of biometric changes in both eyes. It would be valuable for future research to investigate the impact of monochromatic light wavelengths independently causing comparable blur in both eyes. Lastly, it is known that both short- and long-term variations in eye length are associated with changes in choroidal thickness. However, this study did not aim to assess the interaction between axial length and choroid (whether changes in axial length are caused by choroidal changes or vice versa). Further research is needed to determine the impact of chromatic signals associated with LCA, neuronal signaling pathways (such as the blue-cone mediated ON pathway), the role of ipRGCs and melanopsin, reduced levels of retinoic acid, and larger retinal blur circle on ocular biometry in humans under monochromatic light conditions. Elucidating the mechanisms involved in these processes was beyond the scope of the present study.

CONCLUSION

The study's conclusion highlights that blue light exposure has a predominant effect over hyperopic defocus, leading to axial length shortening in human eyes. These findings suggest that shorter wavelength exposure, such as blue light, could potentially be utilized to halt the progression of myopia.

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